

**I SHO’BA. GLOBAL IQLIM ILISHI, UNING DARYOLAR, KO’LLAR VA
SUV OMBORLARI GIDROLOGIK VA GIDROKIMYOVIY REJIMI HAMDA ULARNING
SUV RESURLARIGA TA’SIRI**

**I СЕКЦИЯ. ГЛОБАЛЬНОЕ ПОТЕПЛЕНИЕ КЛИМАТА, ЕГО ВЛИЯНИЕ НА
ГИДРОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ
И ГИДРОХИМИЧЕСКИЙ РЕЖИМ И ВОДНЫЕ РЕСУРСЫ РЕК,
ОЗЕР И ВОДОХРАНИЛИЩ**

**SECTION I. GLOBAL WARMING AND ITS IMPACT ON THE HYDROLOGICAL AND
HYDROCHEMICAL REGIME AND WATER RESOURCES OF RIVERS,
LAKES AND RESERVOIRS**

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**SHORT-TERM VARIABILITY OF DISSOLVED OXYGEN, TEMPERATURE, AND
PROBABLE MIXING-INFLUENCED ZONES IN THE MATLA–CHANNEL–BIDYADHARI
ESTUARINE SYSTEM, INDIAN SUNDARBANS**

Abstract. The present study investigates the short-term longitudinal and vertical variability of dissolved oxygen (DO) and temperature along the Matla, Channel, and Bidyadhari transects of the Indian Sundarbans estuarine system during 30 August, 1 September, and 3 September 2024. Field observations were carried out at 29 stations using a CTD profiler, and the measured vertical profiles were processed into longitudinal–depth transect sections. The results reveal clear spatial heterogeneity across the estuarine network over the three sampling dates. Among the three reaches, the Matla transect exhibited the highest variability and the strongest oxygen depletion, with DO declining to about 4.0–5.0 mgL⁻¹ in deeper sectors on 3 September. In contrast, the Channel transect remained comparatively more homogeneous, with DO generally ranging from 5.5 to 6.5 mgL⁻¹, indicating relatively stronger vertical exchange. The Bidyadhari transect showed intermediate behaviour, with DO mostly around 5.5–5.9 mgL⁻¹ and a localized subsurface oxygen-rich core reaching 6.0–6.3 mgL⁻¹ on 3 September. Temperature remained generally high in all three reaches, characterized by warm surface waters and localized cooler bottom wedges. Probable mixing-influenced zones were identified qualitatively from contour compression, wedge-like structures, and abrupt vertical transitions, and were most evident in the Matla reach. Overall, the study demonstrates that short-term estuarine variability in the Sundarbans is substantial and that transect-based analysis provides valuable insight into water-column structure, localized oxygen stress, and probable mixing influence in this climate-sensitive estuarine system.

Keywords: dissolved oxygen (DO), CTD profiler, Temperature, Matla, Channel, Bidyadhari.

Introduction. Estuaries are highly dynamic transition zones where river discharge, tides, stratification, and biogeochemical processes interact continuously. Because of this, water-quality variables such as dissolved oxygen (DO) and temperature often vary strongly in both the vertical and longitudinal directions. Estuarine studies have shown that mixing and stratification are major controls on water-column structure, while warming and reduced vertical exchange can increase the risk of low-oxygen conditions [2],[5].

The Indian Sundarbans estuarine system is a mangrove-dominated environment known for strong spatial and temporal variability in water quality. Earlier work from the Sundarbans has shown that temperature, DO, turbidity, nutrients, and tidal circulation jointly influence estuarine metabolism and ecosystem functioning. This makes section-wise analysis more useful than isolated point observations for understanding local hydrographic behaviour [1],[6].

In this study, dissolved oxygen and temperature were examined along the Matla, Channel, and Bidyadhari transects for 30 August, 1 September, and 3 September 2024. The aim was to compare

short-term longitudinal and vertical variability among the three reaches and to identify probable mixing-influenced zones from contour structure. Since salinity, density, and current data are not included here, the mixing interpretation is kept qualitative [2],[5].

Study area and Materials and method: The study was carried out in the Indian Sundarbans estuarine system along the Matla, Channel, and Bidyadhari reaches. Field observations were made using a CTD profiler on 30 August, 1 September, and 3 September 2024. Measurements were collected at about 2 km spacing along 29 stations (A1–A21 and B1–B8) covering nearly 56 km of the estuarine transect. Vertical profiles of temperature, dissolved oxygen, salinity, electrical conductivity, chlorophyll fluorescence, turbidity, and pH were recorded at each station. For the present study, only temperature and dissolved oxygen were used to prepare longitudinal–depth transect sections. Potential mixing-influenced zones were identified qualitatively from compressed contours, wedge-like structures, and abrupt vertical or longitudinal transitions.

Figure 1. Study area map showing the location of the Indian Sundarbans estuarine system and the distribution of sampling stations along the Matla, Channel, and Bidyadhari reaches used for transect-based water-quality profiling.

Results and Discussion: Matla transect. The Matla transect showed the highest short-term variability. On 30 August 2024, surface dissolved oxygen (DO) in the seaward sector was relatively high, about $6.5\text{--}7.0\text{ mg L}^{-1}$, while deeper and landward waters remained lower, mostly around $4.2\text{--}5.5\text{ mg L}^{-1}$. On 1 September 2024, the section became more moderate, with most values between 5.0 and 6.5 mg L^{-1} . On 3 September 2024, the strongest oxygen depletion appeared, with much of the central and deeper zone declining to about $4.0\text{--}5.0\text{ mg L}^{-1}$. Temperature ranged from about 29.2 to $32.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, with a warm surface layer and cooler deeper water, indicating repeated short-term water-column reorganization.

Channel Transect: The Channel transect was comparatively more uniform. On 30 August 2024, surface DO was about $7.0\text{--}8.0\text{ mg L}^{-1}$, while most deeper waters remained around $5.0\text{--}5.5\text{ mg L}^{-1}$. On 1 September 2024, DO was more homogeneous, mostly between 5.6 and 6.5 mg L^{-1} , and on 3 September 2024 it remained fairly uniform at about $5.5\text{--}5.9\text{ mg L}^{-1}$. Unlike Matla, the Channel did not show strong localized oxygen depletion. Temperature varied approximately between 29.8 and $31.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, with a relatively stable structure and weaker vertical gradients than Matla.

Dissolved oxygen Transect Cross section at Matla on 30th Aug, 01st sep, 3rd sep 2024

Figure 2. Longitudinal–depth transect sections of dissolved oxygen (DO) and temperature along the Matla reach on 30 August, 1 September, and 3 September 2024, showing strong short-term variability, localized oxygen depletion, and probable mixing-influenced zones.

Dissolved oxygen Transect Cross section at Channel on 30th Aug, 01st sep, 3rd sep 2024

Figure 3. Longitudinal–depth transect sections of dissolved oxygen (DO) and temperature along the Channel reach on 30 August, 1 September, and 3 September 2024, indicating comparatively uniform water-column structure and relatively stronger vertical mixing.

Bidyadhari Transect: The Bidyadhari transect showed intermediate behaviour between Matla and the Channel. On 30 August 2024, DO was mostly around 5.4–6.0 mg L⁻¹, except for a localized oxygen-rich surface patch reaching about 6.6–7.0 mg L⁻¹. On 1 September 2024, the section became fairly uniform, with most values around 5.5–5.9 mg L⁻¹. On 3 September 2024, a distinct subsurface oxygen-rich core developed between about 53 and 59 km, where DO reached about 6.0–6.3 mg L⁻¹. Temperature ranged roughly from 29.5 to 30.4 °C, with localized warm-core features in the mid-to-

deep layer.

Dissolved oxygen Transect Cross section at Bidyadhari on 30th Aug, 01st sep, 3rd sep 2024

Figure 4. Longitudinal–depth transect sections of dissolved oxygen (DO) and temperature along the Bidyadhari reach on 30 August, 1 September, and 3 September 2024, showing intermediate variability with localized subsurface oxygen-rich and warm-core features.

Comparative interpretation. Overall, the three transects showed clear short-term heterogeneity. Matla was the most dynamic and oxygen-sensitive reach, the Channel was the most vertically uniform and comparatively well mixed, and Bidyadhari showed moderate conditions with localized subsurface organization. These results indicate that a single station or surface-only observation would not capture the full estuarine structure.

Conclusion: This study showed that the Matla–Channel–Bidyadhari estuarine system was highly variable even over a short three-day period. Matla exhibited the greatest variability and the strongest localized oxygen depletion, the Channel remained comparatively more homogeneous and better oxygenated, and Bidyadhari showed moderate DO with localized subsurface features. The contour structure further suggests that probable mixing-influenced zones were unevenly distributed across the system, being strongest in Matla, broad in the Channel, and localized in Bidyadhari. Since the interpretation is based only on DO and temperature transects, these zones should be treated as qualitative indicators rather than direct measures of mixing intensity. Overall, the results highlight the value of transect-based analysis for understanding estuarine water-column structure in a climate-sensitive system such as the Sundarbans.

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ДАРЁЛАРНИНГ ЕР ОСТИ СУВЛАРИДАН ТЎЙИНИШИ ҲАҚИДАГИ ИЛМИЙ ҚАРАШЛАРНИНГ ШАКЛЛАНИШИ ВА РИВОЖЛАНИШИ

Аннотация. Мақола дарёларнинг ер ости сувларидан тўйиниши ҳақидаги илк илмий қарашларнинг шаклланиши ва ривожланиши тарихини ўрганишга бағишланган. Шу мақсадда, дарёларнинг ер ости сувларидан тўйиниши ҳақидаги ёзма илмий манбалар тўпланди. Уларнинг таҳлиллари асосида дарёларнинг ер ости сувларидан тўйиниши ҳақидаги илк илмий қарашлар, тасавурларнинг шаклланиши ва уларнинг ривожланиши масалалари беш босқичга бўлиб ўрганилди.

Калит сўзлар: дарёлар, тўйиниши манбалари, ер ости сувлари, илмий қарашлар, шаклланиши, ривожланиши босқичлари, ўрганиши.

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ИСТОРИИ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ И РАЗВИТИЯ НАУЧНЫХ ВЗГЛЯДОВ ПИТАНИИ РЕК ЗА СЧЕТ ПОДЗЕМНЫХ ВОД

Аннотация. Статья посвящена изучению истории формирования и развития научных взглядов питания рек за счет подземных вод. С этой целью были, собраны письменные научные источники о питании рек подземными водами. На основе их анализа изучены первоначальные научные взгляды, формирования идей о питании рек подземными водами, и периоды их развития разделены на пять этапов.

Ключевые слова: реки, источники питания, подземные воды, научные взгляды, формирование, этапы развитие, изучение.

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THE HISTORY OF THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENTIFIC VIEWS ON RIVERS' FEEDING BY GROUNDWATER

Abstract. This article examines the formation and development of initial scientific views on groundwater recharge in rivers. For this purpose, written scientific literature on groundwater recharge sources was collected. Based on an analysis of these sources, the first scientific views on groundwater recharge in rivers were examined, along with the formation of these ideas and their development, in five stages.

Key words: rivers, sources of nutrition, groundwater, scientific views, formation, development, study.

Кириш. Дарёларнинг ер ости сувларидан тўйиниши ҳақидаги дастлабки илмий қарашларнинг шаклланиши жуда қадим замонларга бориб тақалади. Бунинг асосий сабаби арид минтақалардаги дарёларнинг кам сувли, яъни межень даврида асосан ер ости сувларидан